

Change log

CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2026-2028

V01.00

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Introduction

To maintain alignment with practice and to ensure the requirements meet community needs, the CoreTrustSeal Requirements and supporting guidance are subject to feedback and revision every three years. The new Requirements will be in place from 2026-2028, all existing certifications under previous requirements remain valid until due for renewal.

The CoreTrustSeal mission continues to be provision of a low barrier to entry 'core' level of requirements that are broadly applicable to repository data service providers that ensure the long term preservation of the digital objects they curate for the benefit of a defined designated community.

This change log document accompanies the release (2025-11) of the revised CoreTrustSeal Requirement extended guidance for 2026-2028: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17659852>. It describes the changes implemented based on Board proposals and community feedback.

The changes proposed by the Board based on their experience of certifying against the Requirements were overwhelmingly supported by community feedback. The Guidance has been editorially reviewed for additional clarity, to minimise perceived overlap between Requirements, and with an international audience in mind. Many of the excellent proposals received during the feedback period have been incorporated into the Guidance where they were within the scope of a 'core' Requirements set. Some proposals were not incorporated due to being too challenging for the broad range of repositories, or too domain or disciplinary specific to be included in the guidance. There were some proposals for which there is not yet sufficient community consensus for integration; some of these will form part of future CoreTrustSeal work to identify and address community priorities for clarification.

Changes

Background Information & Context (R.0)

(2) Repository type.

Fixed typing error.

Was: "ISelect a repository type"

Is now: "Select a repository type"

(5) Levels of Curation and Preservation

Was: Levels of Curation

Changed to the newly proposed levels of curation and preservation.

2026-2028 text:

- Z. Level Zero. Content distributed as deposited. Unattended deposit-storage-access.
- D. Deposit Compliance
- C. Initial Curation
- A. Active preservation

Was: Select all relevant types from:

- A. Content distributed as deposited
- B. Basic curation – e.g. brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
- C. Enhanced curation – e.g. conversion to new formats during ingest, enhancement of documentation and metadata
- D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data

Response

Guidance

A repository must demonstrate that it assures long-term accessibility and understandability of data as the needs of the Designated Community change. This is less likely to be possible at curation levels A or B, because without normalising submitted file formats to a common preservation format, it may be difficult to perform format migrations in the future depending on the heterogeneity of the collection. Similarly, lack of rich metadata and documentation may pose a risk concerning the continued usability of the data.

It is recognised that a repository may offer different levels of curation to different digital objects. It is important that this is clear to depositors, users, and to CoreTrustSeal Reviewers.

More than one option (A, B, C, or D) of the level (or extent) of curation can be selected, depending on the type of data and curation terms agreed with the depositor. For each level selected add some concise information on how the respective levels are reached e.g. automatic checks of metadata, intellectual checks and editing of documentation, file format identification, transformation to preservation file formats, etc.

When a repository performs curation at more than one level, further information should be added on the proportion of the data in the collection curated to the respective levels. In this case, applicants should take care that responses to the Requirements state any relevant differences in workflows or employed measures for each selected curation level.

All levels of curation assume (1) initial deposits are retained unchanged and that edits are only made on copies of those originals, (2) metadata that enables the Designated Community to understand and use the data independently (i.e., without having to consult the original creator) is present at deposit or added by the repository, and (3) ongoing measures for active preservation are in place for the greater part of the collection(s).

Annotations/edits must fall within the terms of the license agreed with the data depositor and be clearly within the skillset of those undertaking the curation. Thus, the repository will be expected to demonstrate that any such annotations/edits are undertaken and documented by appropriate experts and that the integrity of all original copies is maintained.

Extended Guidance

Reviewers will expect a higher level of formal provenance, integrity, and version management (change logs, etc.) as curation levels progress from A through to D.

(6) Cooperation and outsourcing to third parties, partners and host organisations.

Additional text added to clarify the meaning of the term 'responsibility' in this context.

Text added: In the CoreTrustSeal framework, responsibility refers to the applicant's ultimate accountability for meeting the requirements of certification. While specific tasks or services (e.g. storage, curation, access systems) may be outsourced or delegated to third parties, the applicant remains responsible for ensuring that: the outsourced functions are carried out as agreed; roles and responsibilities are clearly defined and documented; evidence of compliance can be provided to reviewers; and the Designated Community can rely on the repository to preserve data and metadata for the long term. Outsourcing does not transfer responsibility; it only shifts operational duties.

(7) Applicants renewing their CoreTrustSeal certification: summary of significant changes since last application.

Text updated to more clearly explain the expected depth of answer.

2026-2028 text: CoreTrustSeal certification has an expectation of continuous improvement over time. Repositories undergoing recertification should summarise key changes since their last application, including any changes to their technical systems, Designated Community or governance/funding, as well as progress on Requirements. This summary should specify the area of change, provide a brief description, indicate the timing, and outline the impact on the repository.

Was: CoreTrustSeal certification has an expectation of continuous improvement over time. Repositories undergoing recertification should highlight briefly any significant changes including to technical systems, Designated Community or funding during the previous three years. This could include any steps taken to move from 'In Progress' to 'Implemented' Requirements since the last certification.

Organisational Infrastructure

Mission & Scope (R01)

Addition to the Requirement description to emphasise the focus on active preservation.

2026-2028 text: R01. The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and actively preserve digital objects.

Was: R01. The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve digital objects.

Continuity of Service (R03)

Additions to the guidance to clarify possible evidence further and emphasise the decisions made around compliance levels.

2026-2028 text: **Guidance**

The repository must have measures in place to address the risks inherent in changing circumstances, including in mission and/or scope. This Requirement covers the stable management of repository services over time (business continuity) and the response when services have problems (disaster recovery). It also includes preparations for handover of digital objects and services to another repository (succession planning). The deposit, storage, preservation, and access services offered by the repository to depositors and users are all in scope.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The functions and services offered by the repository to depositors and users.
- The approach to rapid changes of circumstance and long-term planning.
- The options for relocation or transition of the activity to another repository. For example, the case of cessation of funding due to an unexpected withdrawal of funding, or a shift of host institution interests. Such options should also include the levels of service that will be continued at relocation or transition (e.g. data retention only, or including other services).
- The repository approach to managing policies, procedures and other business information over time.

Even though succession agreements may be hard to achieve it is important to acknowledge the possibility that a repository will cease to function or exist. Applications can be certified and recertified with compliance level “In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase”. If there is no formal, written agreement between the repository and a successor then the compliance level cannot be higher than “In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase”. Such an agreement can be with another repository to take over holdings, but is not limited to this and may also concern a software or services provider.

Any technical aspects of business continuity, and disaster and succession planning should be covered in R15 (Technical infrastructure).

Was: **Guidance**

The repository must have measures in place to address the risks inherent in changing circumstances, including in mission and/or scope. This Requirement covers the stable management of repository services over time (business continuity) and the response when services have problems (disaster recovery). It also includes preparations for handover of digital objects and services to another repository (succession planning). The deposit, storage, preservation, and access services offered by the repository to depositors and users are all in scope.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The functions and services offered by the repository to depositors and users.
- The approach to rapid changes of circumstance and long-term planning.
- The options for relocation or transition of the activity to another repository. For example, the case of cessation of funding due to an unexpected withdrawal of funding, or a shift of host institution interests.
- The repository approach to managing policies, procedures and other business information over time.

Even though succession agreements may be hard to achieve it is important to acknowledge the possibility that a repository will cease to function or exist. If there is no formal, written agreement between the repository and a successor then the compliance level cannot be

higher than “In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase”.

Any technical aspects of business continuity, and disaster and succession planning should be covered in R15 (Technical infrastructure).

Governance & Resources (R05)

Addition of details on the suggestion for diagrams.

2026-2028: Guidance

This Requirement reflects a need for transparency of financing, governance, responsibilities, and decision making. Evidence should demonstrate that the repository has a clear system of governance and sufficient human and financial resources to carry out its mission.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- Up-to-date organizational chart and description outlining the governance structure, key bodies, and reporting lines; it is important to show the hierarchy, roles, and relationships between management, operational teams, etc. Descriptions and diagrams of governance bodies, groups and hierarchies.
- Timescales for provision and renewal of funding for operational costs and recruitment; it is understood that permanent, ongoing funding cannot be perfectly quantified or guaranteed.
- Evidence that the repository is, or is hosted by, a recognized institution (supporting long-term stability and sustainability) appropriate to its Designated Community.
- Demonstrate that the repository can meet its obligations, including sufficient funding, staff resources, IT resources, and a budget for external engagement when necessary.

The availability of appropriate expertise is covered under Expertise (R06) below.

Was: Guidance

This Requirement reflects a need for transparency of financing, governance, responsibilities, and decision making. Evidence should demonstrate that the repository has a clear system of governance and sufficient human and financial resources to carry out its mission.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- Descriptions and diagrams of governance bodies, groups and hierarchies.
- Timescales for provision and renewal of funding for operational costs and recruitment; it is understood that permanent, ongoing funding cannot be perfectly quantified or guaranteed.
- Evidence that the repository is, or is hosted by, a recognized institution (supporting long-term stability and sustainability) appropriate to its Designated Community.
- Demonstrate that the repository can meet its obligations, including sufficient funding, staff resources, IT resources, and a budget for external engagement when necessary.

The availability of appropriate expertise is covered under Expertise (R06) below.

Digital Object Management

Provenance and authenticity (R07)

Example statement added for improved clarity

Addition: “An example of an informative statement could be ‘A relational database maintains a timestamped record of metadata changes, including which logged-in account made the change.’”

Deposit, Appraisal & Accessibility (R08)

Was: Deposit & Appraisal (R08)

Requirement name updated and slight changes made in the text to emphasise accessibility over understandability in this Requirement.

2026-2028: Guidance

The appraisal function during deposit is critical to evaluate whether digital objects meet all criteria for selection and to ensure appropriate management for their preservation. Appraisal ensures that deposited digital objects are relevant and are, or can become, accessible understandable to the Designated Community. Accessible means that users should easily be able to find, retrieve, and use the data and metadata.

Was: **Guidance**

The appraisal function during deposit is critical to evaluate whether digital objects meet all criteria for selection and to ensure appropriate management for their preservation. Appraisal ensures that deposited digital objects are relevant and are, or can become, understandable to the Designated Community.

Preservation plan (R09)

Some updates made to the guidance to improve clarity.

2026-2028 text: Guidance

The repository, depositors, and Designated Community need to understand the level of responsibility undertaken for the long-term preservation of data and metadata. This exceeds bit level integrity alone and covers plans to respond to potential future changes which may impact the understandability and reusability of data and metadata over time. Procedures must be documented and their completion assured.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The documented approach to preservation, including whether this involves format migration, emulation, etc. Ensuring bit level integrity is vital but not sufficient for preservation.
- File formats and metadata schemas for long term preservation.
- How the level of responsibility for the preservation of each item is defined.
- Plans related to future migrations or similar measures to address the threat of obsolescence.
- Actions relevant to preservation specified in documentation, including custody transfer, submission information criteria, and preservation information metadata.
- Measures to ensure these actions are taken.
- Any minimum stated retention and/or preservation periods.
- How often the digital objects are re-appraised and the possible outcomes of reappraisal.

- The repository approach to deleting/removing data and metadata from collection/holdings including the impact on persistent identifiers as well as the availability and curation of tombstone records.

The rights of the repository, including the right to preserve, are covered under Rights Management (R02). Bit level integrity is covered under Storage and Integrity (R14). Acceptable file formats at deposit should be covered under Deposit and Appraisal (R08). Measures to ensure that file formats, schemas and content are appropriate to the Designated Community should be covered under Reuse (R13).

Was: **Guidance**

The repository, depositors, and Designated Community need to understand the level of responsibility undertaken for the long-term preservation of data and metadata. Procedures must be documented and their completion assured.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The documented approach to preservation, including whether this involves format migration, emulation, etc. Ensuring bit level integrity is vital but not sufficient for preservation.
- File formats and metadata schemas for long term preservation.
- How the level of responsibility for the preservation of each item is defined.
- Plans related to future migrations or similar measures to address the threat of obsolescence.
- Actions relevant to preservation specified in documentation, including custody transfer, submission information criteria, and preservation information metadata.
- Measures to ensure these actions are taken.
- Any minimum stated retention and/or preservation periods.
- How often the digital objects are re-appraised and the possible outcomes of reappraisal.
- The repository approach to deleting/removing data and metadata from collection/holdings including the impact on persistent identifiers.

The rights of the repository, including the right to preserve, are covered under Rights Management (R02). Bit level integrity is covered under Storage and Integrity (R14). Acceptable file formats at deposit should be covered under Deposit and Appraisal (R08). Measures to ensure that file formats, schemas and content are appropriate to the Designated Community should be covered under Reuse (R13).

Workflows (R11)

Suggestion added for applicants to illustrate their workflows in a diagram for increased understandability for reviewers.

2026-2028 text: This Requirement confirms that all workflows are documented. You can include a diagram to illustrate this. It should be noted if there are different workflows for different levels of security mentioned in the Legal and Ethical (R04) response statement. Workflows may include qualitative and quantitative checking of outputs, but any detail on checks and compliance should be addressed under Quality Assurance (R10).

Was: This Requirement confirms that all workflows are documented. It should be noted if there are different workflows for different levels of security mentioned in the Legal and Ethical (R04) response statement. Workflows may include qualitative and quantitative

checking of outputs, but any detail on checks and compliance should be addressed under Quality Assurance (R10).

Discovery and Identification (R12)

Minor textual change to increase accuracy.

2026-2028 text: Effective data and metadata sharing discovery is key to resource discovery. Once discovered, digital objects should be referenceable through full citations, including persistent identifiers (PIDs) to help ensure that they can be retrieved into the future.

Was: Effective data and metadata sharing discovery is key to resource discovery. Once discovered, digital objects should be referenceable through full citations, including persistent identifiers (PIDs) to help ensure that they can be accessed into the future.